

WORKINGAGE

Smart Working Environments for All Ages

WorkingAge will use innovative Human-Computer-Interaction (HCI) methods to measure the user emotional/cognitive/health state and create communication paths.

The purpose is to promote healthy habits of users in their working environment and daily living activities in order to improve their working and living conditions.

An integrated digital solution, the WorkingAge Of Well-being (WAOW) Tool, will support this by studying the profile of the >45 (years old) workers and the working place requirements in three different working environments (Office, Teleworking and Manufacturing), both elements (user profile and work environment) will be considered. Information obtained will be used for the creation of friendly interventions that will lead to healthy ageing inside and outside the working environment.

WorkingAge will test and validate an integrated solution that learns the user's behaviour, health data and preferences, and through continuous data collection and analysis will interact naturally with the user. This innovative system will provide assistance for workers in their everyday routine in the form of reminders, risk avoidance and recommendations. In this way, the WorkingAge project will create a modular and scalable product that will empower both companies and employees, easing their professional lives by attenuating the impact of ageing and improving their autonomy, work conditions, health and well-being.

The consortium is formed by the balance collaboration of international level entities represented by:

- 3 Universities (UCAM, POLIMI, RWTH)
- 4 SMEs (GC, BS, AUD, TMA)
- 1 RTD centre (ITCL)
- 2 Big enterprises and industries (EXUS, TPZ)
- 2 Associations (EENA-112, INTRAS)

WorkingAge involves combining technology with empathy, to create well-being experiences for people over 45 years to make sense and adapt the work environments to a world that is constantly changing

MILESTONES

The WorkingAge tool will combine Human-Computer-Interaction (HCI) methods supported by different measurements reflecting the user's cognitive and emotional states for giving recommendations to workers interacting in their usual working environment

The WorkingAge project aims at making a step forward in technology for new working environment possibilities. The project's objectives have been structured in different areas:

- Respond to ageing, which is a challenge in today's society, emphasizing the need for changes in intervention models to guarantee the quality of life of older workers
- Try to find and promote innovative solutions for people who can and want to work until older ages
- Provide digitally enabled adaptive services and solutions
- Create a Smart Working Environment
- Develop a user-centred design, with new intuitive ways of human computer interaction

WANT TO KNOW MORE ?

- www.workingage.eu
- <https://www.linkedin.com/in/workingage-EU/>
- https://twitter.com/Workingage_EU

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